

LINGUODIDACTIC AND PSYCHOLOGICAL CRITERIA OF LANGUAGE LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the correct formation of the learning process in the development of students' speaking skills, the development and improvement of technology in language education, the inclusion of the product of consciousness, memory and thinking in the literary normative form of language, its linguodidactical basis and psychological norms.

INTRODUCTION. The evolving and improving technology of education, along with other disciplines, plays a large-scale general pedagogical role in language education. Improving a student's speaking skills is a fact that does not require proof that the content of language education, the learning process, and its proper formation depend on the fact that speech has become a reality using the means of language expression. It occurs in the process of conscious movement of the members of speech. The means of expression of language, which is a spiritual phenomenon, become reality when it passes into the will of speech. Thus, the task of speech is to bring the product of the harmonious

activity of consciousness, memory and thinking into a form that is understandable to all, a literary norm, to materialize it (to turn it into information) and to convey it to the listener. At the same time, the methodology of teaching the native language has a linguodidactic basis, including the study of language units based not only on grammatical features but also on lexical meanings, differentiation of general and specific phenomena, vocabulary development, oral speech, independent text formation, its diversity, and methodological fluency.

One of the main principles of language research proposed by sociolinguists was the principle of the inseparable unity of the

language form and its functional use in the speech and non-speech context.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY. Well-known linguists and methodologists in Uzbek linguistics H. G'. Pe'matov, N. M. Mahmudov, A. Nurmonov, A. Q. The Gulyamovs started [1].

N.V. Ippolitova, E. M. Vereshchagina, V. G. Kostomarov, V. S. Krasilnikova, I. V. Kolmogorova, J. Ya. Lopasova the development of this direction by scholars such as the idea that the educational process can only be effective when culture is indirectly expressed, when culture is dominant in the formation of personality.

N.V. Ippolitova, I.V. Kolmogorova, V.S. Krasilnikova, V.V. Russian scholars such as Safonova have three components as a means of pedagogical activity that functionally play the role of lingvodidactic bases and principles, conditions, tools of linguistic didactic bases and psychological measures at different stages of the educational process: practical-action, knowledge-information, value-oriented; described the process of cultural development of the individual as a procedural representation [2].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY. In language education, the introduction of speech, which is a product of the student's mind, memory and thinking, into a literary normative form, the definition of lingvodidactic bases and psychological norms of its materialization..

DISCUSSION. Of great interest to researchers are segments of speech that have some semantic unity and without which it is impossible to implement the speaker's speech plan. This approach to the study of the functional nature of language has become widespread in the framework

of the theory of speech acts. This theory, as one of the sections of pragmatics, divides the subject of its research, everyday language, into speech utterances (Sprechakte), which are natural, situationally conditioned sentences through which the speaker expresses what he wants to say, and at the same time how the utterance should be understood.

In this sense, statements are given the meaning of action, and they are considered as speech acts. In other words, this theory is an attempt to describe speech acts in the form of basic units of communication expressing various speech intentions - promises, requests, threats, orders, etc.

The term "speech act" is based on the understanding that when analyzing verbal statements, in addition to phonological, syntactic and semantic aspects, it is necessary to take into account both pragmatic factors motivating speech action and non-linguistic factors of situational context.

The speech act correlates with the method of verbalization of the speaker's intention and has the ability to reflect the social, psychological and linguistic aspects of the language. The orientation of the communicative method to speech acts leads to a shift in emphasis in language teaching from structure to communicative functions, and the task of teaching becomes the assimilation by students of means important for communication.

The demands put forward by the communicative method to strengthen the practical orientation of teaching are consistent with the general attitude of linguistic pragmatics, in particular the theory of speech acts, emphasizing the need to know what speech actions and in

what communication situation can be carried out using certain means.

The assessment of the semantic content of the utterance from the position of the action rendered, as well as the analysis of speech acts from the point of view of their functions, open up new opportunities for teaching foreign languages. Accordingly, one of the features of the communicative method is the organization of educational material | on a conceptual basis.

The linguistics of the text was of great importance for the formation and development of the communicative method [3].

In contrast to structural linguistics or generative grammar, which considered the sentence as the highest unit of linguistic analysis, since the mid-60s of the XX century.

Researchers who have dealt with this problem have come to the conclusion that the highest unit of language is not a sentence, but a text.

Linguistic analysis of the text is important because it helps to understand the relationship between different sides of the communicative process. "It is in this sense that the linguistic theory of discourse is not only important in linguistics, but also serves as a basis for the study of discourse by other disciplines, which contributes to the further integration of discursive analysis in the general study of language and communication" [4, 13].

The discursive analysis of the text is very relevant for the communicative method. Speech perception or speech production is associated with the understanding /transmission of meaning, and it should be based on discourse — a multi-level education that shows a person's ability to

think, and at the same time confirms that he has ideas about speech and non-speech means and the rules of their application [5].

The linguistics of the text made it possible to better understand the semantic structure of the text on the basis of an objective analysis of linguistic means: to show which of them are carriers of meaning and by what signs they are recognized. The data of the linguistics of the text are also used in the selection of educational texts.

The researchers' awareness of the insufficient effectiveness of teaching methods based on the theory of behaviorism, which was strongly criticized for its one-sidedness, led to the fact that in the second half of the 60s of the XX century, educational theories arose that opposed the idea of a person as a black box, which can be manipulated through external stimuli. Scientific research has led to the conclusion that cognitive psychology has the greatest prospects, which is also called "psychology of information processing" [5, 58].

Trying to identify the complexity of the cognition process, cognitive psychology explores the problem of how people acquire and express knowledge about the world around them, how they organize and use this knowledge.

Based on the linguistic and psychological data discussed above, conclusions can be drawn that are important for understanding the essence of the communicative method. In the process of communication as a special kind of human activity aimed at establishing and maintaining communication and used to transmit information between people, two

sides interact — linguistic and social, since any utterance made in a particular communication situation is preceded by a very wide background of preconditions affecting its organization. The language is used taking into account the communication situation and its influence on the verbal strategy of the speaker/writer, listener/reader, i.e. taking into account the pragmatic effect, which excludes the possibility of the existence of isolated sentences created outside the communicative context. The units of communication are a certain kind of actions (Sprechafcte): statements, requests, questions, apologies, expressions of gratitude, etc. The communicative significance of the structural elements of the speech act (words, phrases, sentences) is revealed in the discourse that determines their functions and relationships. The generation of a speech act is preceded by the formation of a speech intention (intention), which takes into account prior knowledge about the communication partner, as well as the purpose, subject, place and time of the utterance.

As a result of psychological-lingvodidactic analysis of the types of listening comprehension and speaking speech activities, we emphasize that the process of developing oral speech skills should be based on the following aspects:

has a single structural structure as a type of oral speech activity, which is manifested through 3 stages -

motivational-stimulating, analytical-synthetic and control-executive stages; the uniqueness of psychophysiological mechanisms (memory, predictive logical thinking mechanisms); the interaction of auditory and motor analyzers in both the process of listening comprehension and speech; the functional occurrence of internal speech in both the processes of speech reception and speech narration.

Given the national-cultural approach as an important pedagogical condition for achieving goals in language teaching, it is necessary to determine whether students have a positive motivation to learn the language, which can be provided by many factors and methods and depends not only on students but also on teacher creativity and pedagogical skills.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, the general (similar) psycholinguistic characteristics of the types of speech activities allow to increase the efficiency of the development process in a complex system, in combination with listening comprehension and speaking skills, and to save time in training. Of particular importance is the fact that speech and listening comprehension are subject to general psychophysiological mechanisms of speech activity, including the fact that the mechanism of logical thinking is simultaneously active in both speech processes.

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